

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

Muhammad Alang Khirun Nizar

Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi Bina Karya

ABSTRACT: This research uses a quantitative approach, where the symptoms will be measured using numbers. The results of this study, the multiple linear regression equation $Y = 15,676 + 0.681X_1 - 0.080X_2$. This means that the principal's leadership style variables and motivation have a significant relationship with teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi. The coefficient determinant of R^2 is 0.502 or 50.2%. This means that the Principal leadership style variable (X_1) and motivation (X_2) can explain the teacher performance variable (Y) by 50.2%, the remaining 49.8% (100% - 50.2%) is explained by other variables that not included in this study such as reward, punishment, communication, education level, years of service, work absenteeism rates, etc., which were not thorough in this study.

After testing the hypothesis that the calculated value of 5.529 was obtained. With $\alpha = 5\%$, $dk = 46 - 3 = 43$ obtained a table value of 1.681. From these figures it can be seen that $t_{count} (5.529) > t_{table} (1.681)$, as well as the significance value of $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded if the hypothesis is accepted. After testing the hypothesis that the t-value is -0.925. With $\alpha = 5\%$, $dk = 46 - 3 = 43$ obtained a table value of 1.681. From these figures it can be seen that $t_{count} (-0.925) < t_{table} (1.681)$, as well as the significance value of $0.360 > 0.05$, it can be concluded if the hypothesis is rejected. The third hypothesis proposed states that there is an influence of the Principal's leadership style and motivation on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi. After being tested the Fcount value was 23.703. With $\alpha = 5\%$, $df_1 = 3$, $df_2 = 46 - 3 = 43$ the Ftable value of 2.82 is obtained. From these figures it can be seen that $F_{count} (23.703) > F_{table} (3.26)$, as well as the significance value of $0.000b < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted.

KEYWORDS: Principal's Leadership Style, Work Motivation and Teacher Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education for a nation that is developing like the Indonesian nation today is an absolute necessity that must be developed in line with the demands of development step by step. Education that is managed in an orderly, orderly, and efficient manner can produce something that is able to accelerate the process of civilizing the nation based on the principle of creating general welfare and the intellectual life of our nation, according to the objectives of national education itself.

If education is one of the most important things in the development of human resources, then educators and education staff certainly have a very big responsibility in carrying out this task. So that the quality standards of educators and education personnel need to be improved. Teachers are one of the elements of resources that determine success in education in schools, because teachers are a human element that is very close to students in daily education at school. As educators, teachers are the determining factor in improving the quality of education in schools.

Therefore, educators (teachers) must be able to improve performance in carrying out their duties because education in the future requires quality education professional skills. So that the performance of professional teachers can be a breath of fresh air for success in the world of education in the future. To improve teacher performance in schools, the provision of various types of training and professional education to teachers is certainly needed. According to Abdul Hadi and Nurhayati B., there are two important factors that influence teacher performance in schools, namely the qualification of teacher standards and the relevance of the teacher's field of expertise to teaching assignments.

The problem of leadership always gives an interesting impression because an organization's success or failure is partly determined by the quality of leadership. According to Mulyasa, leadership is a process of influencing the activities of a person or

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

group in an effort to achieve goals in certain situations. So that it can be interpreted that leadership is an action taken by individuals to influence and provide direction to other individuals or groups in a particular organization to achieve predetermined goals. Leadership is one of the main factors in organizational life that plays a key role. Because the leadership of a leader acts as a regulator in the process of cooperation between leaders and individuals and leaders with groups.

Abdul Hadi and Nurhayati B, Education Quality Management (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2010). h. 9.

The leadership of a leader (principal) will be able to distinguish between one organization and another. The leadership style possessed by the leader or principal in leading an organization will affect the performance of the teacher. According to Thoah as quoted by Mulyasa, explaining leadership style is a behavioral norm used by a person when that person tries to influence the behavior of others as he sees it. So that it can be interpreted that leadership style is a way used by a leader in influencing his subordinates.

Teacher performance is the ability of a teacher to carry out the learning process in the classroom in accordance with the goals that have been set. Where this ability has covered several aspects, including: planning teaching and learning programs, implementing the teaching and learning process, creating and maintaining optimal classes, controlling optimal learning conditions, as well as assessment of learning outcomes. Performance is certainly a very important factor in determining the quality of a person's work, including a teacher.

In addition, the principal has not implemented the leadership function optimally to lead his subordinates. Because many of the policies carried out by schools do not come from the thoughts of a principal as a leader, but the policy is based on the thoughts of the teacher as his subordinates. In addition, the principal still treats his subordinates equally without paying attention to individual differences between one teacher and another. Because many of the tasks assigned by the principal to teachers are not considered based on the abilities of the teacher. So that the principal assumes that the tasks given can be carried out by all teachers as their subordinates.

Every school principal is the highest leader in the school organization should have the ability, expertise and skills in running the institution he leads. In addition, the ability to influence and motivate subordinates needs to be possessed in order to improve the performance of their subordinates. The success of a school organization is not only determined by its leader but can also be supported by the utilization of human resources because the weaknesses of a school principal may be found in the advantages possessed by his subordinates (teachers) themselves.

Therefore, the principal as the leader of an organization should be able to see the shortcomings needed by his subordinates so that he can improve teacher performance and performance, among others, by providing encouragement to teachers to carry out their duties in accordance with the rules and directions. Because performance is at least closely related to the leadership of the school organization and also the interests of the teachers themselves, therefore for schools the results of teacher performance assessments are very important.

As for the teacher himself, an assessment of performance can act as feedback on various things such as his abilities, strengths, weaknesses, and potential. so that it can be useful for determining goals, pathways, plans and development for a teacher's career. So it is very important to do a teacher performance assessment on a regular basis. With an assessment of teacher performance, it will certainly be a picture of the success or failure of a teacher in carrying out his duties as an educator.

Teacher performance is the entire effort and ability of a teacher in carrying out the learning process to achieve the goals of education. The teacher's performance includes all activities related to the main task as a teacher and the personal development of a teacher. The main task of a teacher in the learning process can be started from planning learning, implementing, evaluating, providing assessments to follow-up in the learning process. In addition, a teacher is also required to be able to have broad insight in educational science, understanding students and being able to develop the potential possessed by students.

Based on the background that has been described, the researchers are interested in conducting a study entitled The Effect of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi.

¹ *Q.S. Al Anbiyaa'; 21/73.*

THEORITICAL FOUNDATION

1. Definition of Leadership Style

Leadership is the ability to influence a person or group to act or perform a certain goal. This influence has a formal source because the position is in accordance with the organizational structure, because the position and management position is someone can carry out a leadership role. Not all leaders can act as managers, and vice versa not all managers can lead. Just because

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

an organization grants its managers certain formal rights does not mean that they will be able to properly lead the organization. Leaders can emerge from within the group through formal appointments to lead a group.

According to Sudarwan Danim, leadership is all actions taken by a person, both individually and in groups, to coordinate and direct other individuals or groups to achieve predetermined goals. Meanwhile, according to Siagian in Edy Sutrisno, leadership is a person's ability to influence others, where subordinates will do what the leader wants even though personally the subordinates don't like it.

According to Ngalm Purwanto, leadership is a person's ability to influence others so that the people he influences are willing and able to carry out the tasks assigned to him willingly, passionately, there is inner joy, and feels not forced. Meanwhile, according to leadership can be interpreted as a person's ability to move, direct, as well as influence the mindset, the way each member works so that they are independent in working for the sake of accelerating the achievement of the goals that have been set.

Sudarwan Danim, A New Vision of School Management From Bureaucratic Units to Academic Institutions (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2008). h. 204.

Sutrisno Edy, Human Resource Management, (Jakarta; Kencana Prenada Media Group, 2011). h. 213-214.

The above definition can be said that leadership is the ability to influence other people, either individuals or groups. As well as the ability to direct the behavior of individuals or groups to have special abilities or expertise in the field desired by the group, so that subordinates are happy to carry out the tasks assigned to achieve predetermined goals.

Leadership style, contains the understanding as a manifestation of the behavior of a leader, which concerns his ability to lead his subordinates. The embodiment usually forms a certain pattern or shape. According to Nurkolis, leadership style is a pattern of behavior that is preferred by a leader in the process of directing and influencing employees. Meanwhile, according to Miftah Thoha leadership style is a behavioral norm used by a person when that person influences others.

Referring to some of the opinions above, it can be ascertained that the leadership style is a consistent pattern of behavior of the leaders under it so that they are willing to work with pleasure to achieve the goals that have been determined together. Then the principal's leadership style can be interpreted as the perception of teachers and all employees of a school, behavior patterns, or the form of the procedures of a principal in influencing his subordinates to work on a happy basis to achieve the goals of the school.

Ngalm Purwanto, Education Administration and Supervision (Bandung: Rosdakarya Youth, 2005). h. 26.

Wahyudi, Principal Leadership in Learning Organizations (Jakarta; Alfabeta, 2009). h. 120.

Nurkolis, School-Based Management (Jakarta: Grasindo, 2006). h. 167.

Miftah Thoha, Leadership in Management (Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada, 2010). h. 49.

2. Principal's Leadership Function

A principal not only serves as the highest leader in the school, but the principal can be a role model for teachers, employees and school residents. The function and role of the principal in creating a success must start from the planning or process of education and learning in schools first. As a leader, the principal must be able to effectively create changes in the appearance of the group. A leader must be able to move others so that the other person likes to do what a leader wants. Therefore, the principal must know the function of his leadership.

According to Soewadji Lazaruth, there are 3 functions of the principal, namely:

a. Principal as Administrator

The principal functions as an education administrator means to improve the quality of his school, a school principal can repair and develop school facilities such as buildings, equipment or equipment and others included in the field of education administration.

b. Principal as Supervisor

The principal functions as an education supervisor, meaning that quality improvement efforts can also be carried out by improving the quality of teachers and all school staff, for example through meetings, classroom observations, libraries and so on. Then if the principal functions as an educational leader, it means that quality improvement will work well if the teacher is open, creative and has a high work spirit. Such an atmosphere is determined by the form and nature of the leadership carried out by the principal.

c. Principal as Education Leader

A leader or principal has full responsibility and has strong authority to improve the performance of his subordinates. The

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

importance of the role of the principal, as the highest leader in the school must be fair and have high authority in order to support the achievement of a goal for the better. The function of the principal has the task of leading, so the principal is the most central force capable of influencing, moving and convincing others to achieve a goal.

3. Understanding Work Motivation

In a general sense, motivation is said to be a need that drives action towards a certain goal. The definition of motivation as "The process by which behavior is energized and directed" (a process, where the behavior is nurtured and directed) psychologists provide similarities between motives and drives, needs. From the above limitation, it can be concluded that the motive is the background of the individual to act to achieve certain goals.

According to Filmore H. Stanford in Anwar, motivation is a condition that moves people towards a certain goal. When a need is not satisfied, individual drives and activities arise to respond to incentives (incentives) in the desired goal. Achieving goals will make individuals feel satisfied. In motivating employees, the leadership in addition to paying attention and considering qualitatively their psychological abilities and potentials so that they can be contributed as much as possible to the success of the organization, also needs to pay attention to and taking into account the needs of the employees.

Soewadji Lazaruth, Principal and Responsibilities (Yogyakarta: Kanisius, 2004). h. 20.

Anoraga Pandji, Occupational Psychology (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2002). h. 34

Prabu Mangkunegara Anwar, Corporate Psychology (Bandung: Trigenda Karya, 2003). h. 46.

Hasibuan

4. Types of Work Motivation

In organizational life, motivation becomes a very important thing and needs to be held because with motivation it is able to change the behavior of someone who is motivated. Based on this, the types of motivation are as follows:

a. Positive Motivation (Positive Incentives)

This motivation is the manager motivates (stimulates) subordinates by giving prizes to those who excel above standard achievements. With positive motivation, the morale of subordinates will increase because people generally like to accept things that are fine.

b. Negative Motivation (Negative Incentive)

Negative motivation is the manager motivates subordinates with the standard that they will be punished. With this negative motivation, subordinates' morale to work in the short term will increase because they are afraid of being punished, but in the long term it can have bad consequences.

According to Bedjo Siswanto in Ach. Mohyi divides the form of motivation into two, namely:

a. Material incentives

Namely incentives or rewards given to employees in the form of material, such as money or other forms of goods.

b. Non-material incentives

Namely incentives or remuneration (reward) given to employees (subordinates) in the form of non-material, for example praise, awards, promotions, the provision of facilities or convenience factors and so on.

5. Understanding Performance

Performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance which means work performance or actual achievement achieved by someone. Performance (work achievement) is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out the functions according to the responsibilities given to him. According to the behavioral approach in performance management is the quantity or quality of something produced or services provided by someone who does work.

According to Mwita in Gusti Putu, the notion of performance is a work achieved because it provides the company's strategic objectives, customer satisfaction and economic contribution. Meanwhile, according to Hyndman & Anderson as quoted by Dian Wijayanto in performance can be seen from the production model consisting of three stages, namely input, output and results so that performance can be interpreted in terms of efficiency and effectiveness. Performance is work performance, for example, the achievement of turnover, efficiency, profit, and so on. Resources are inputs used to achieve certain performance achievements, in the form of funds, human resources (HR), technology and raw materials.

Performance is a work performance that is a comparison between work and established standards. Performance is the result of work both in quality and quantity achieved by a person in carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities given.

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

Performance is the result or level of success of a person as a whole during a certain period in carrying out tasks compared to various possibilities, such as work standards, targets or targets or predetermined criteria that have been mutually agreed upon.

According to Prawirosentono in Gusti Putu, performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities, in an effort to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics. Performance is basically what employees do or don't do. Employee performance is what influences how much they contribute to the organization.

Performance is very important in an institution to achieve its goals. Performance can run well if employees get salaries as expected, receive training and development, a conducive work environment, receive equal treatment, place employees according to their expertise and get career planning assistance, and there is feedback from an institution.

I Gusti Putu Diva Awantara, Environmental Management System (Jakarta: Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia, 2010). p.10.

Dian Wijayanto, Introduction to Management, (Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2012). h. 2

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6. Factors Affecting Teacher Performance

Many factors affect performance, both related to the workforce and related to the school environment. Various types of work carried out by teachers certainly require clear criteria, because each job certainly has different standards regarding the achievement of the results. According to Suyadi Prawirosentono in Ade Vici Purnama there are several things that affect a company and an employee's performance, namely:

a. Effectiveness and efficiency

The effectiveness of an organization if organizational goals can be achieved in accordance with planned needs, efficiency is related to the number of sacrifices incurred in achieving goals.

b. Responsible

The responsibility is as an inseparable part or as a result of the ownership of the authority.

c. Discipline

Discipline when obeying applicable laws and regulations. Employee discipline is the obedience of the employee concerned in respecting the work agreement with the company where the employee works.

I Gusti Putu Diva Awantara, Environmental Management System. h. 10

Ade Vici Purnama, Effect of Reward and Punishment on Employee Performance Kinerja

d. Initiative

An employee's initiative is related to the power of thought and creativity in the form of ideas for something related to organizational or company goals. Each initiative should receive attention or a positive response from superiors.

RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research is field research, namely direct observation of the object under study, in order to obtain relevant data. This research is a type of quantitative research, in which the symptoms to be studied are measured using numbers. Quantitative data is data in the form of numbers. Thus, this study allows statistical analysis techniques to be used to process the data. According to Sugiyono, quantitative research is a study that uses more logical hypothesis verification, which begins with deductive thinking to derive hypotheses, then conduct field testing and conclusions or hypotheses are drawn based on empirical data.

This research begins by reviewing existing theories and knowledge so that the causes of problems arise. The problem is tested to determine its acceptance or rejection based on data obtained from the field. Data collection techniques are very influential in a study, because the selection of the right data collection techniques will be able to obtain relevant and accurate data. Data collection techniques used in this study are:

1. Questionnaire (Questionnaire). Questionnaires are efficient data collection techniques if the researcher knows for sure the variables to be measured and knows what is expected of the respondents. In addition, the questionnaire is also suitable for use when the number of respondents is quite large. The distribution of questionnaires or questionnaires is given to a predetermined sample that is selected at random (random sampling).
2. Observation. Observation is a research method where researchers make observations directly on the object of research. Observation is a complex process, a process composed of various biological and psychological processes.

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

3. Documentation. Documentation can be done by collecting some information about data and facts related to the problem and research objectives, either from published or unpublished sources of documents, books, scientific journals, newspapers, magazines, websites and others.
4. Literature Study. The literature study used aims to strengthen the truth of the results of the research carried out, by looking for concepts that are relevant to the problem to be studied.

Ade Vici Purnama, Effect of Reward and Punishment on Employee Performance at PT. Kereta Api Indonesia Persero DAOP 8 Surabaya (Surabaya: Faculty of Economics, University of Wijaya Putra, 2015). h. 7

Sugiyono, Understanding Qualitative Research, (Bandung: CV. ALFABETA, 2009). h. 10.

A. Research Results

Multiple linear regression analysis was used in this study with the aim of knowing the effect of variable X (leadership style and work motivation) on variable Y (teacher performance). The multiple linear regression testing used in this research is using the computer program IBM SPSS Statistics version 22 for windows. The results of data processing can be seen in the following table,

Table 1. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	15.676	3.388		4.626	.000		
	Variabel_X1	.681	.123	.813	5.529	.000	.512	1.952
	Variabel_X2	-.080	.087	-.136	-.925	.360	.512	1.952

a. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

Based on these results, the multiple linear regression equation has the formulation: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots$, so that the equation $Y = 15.676 + 0.681X_1 - 0.080X_2$ is obtained.

The t-test is used to determine whether the X1 and X2 variables partially have an effect or not on the Y variable. With the provisions, if the value of sig < 0.05 or tcount > ttable (1.681) then there is an effect of the X variable on the Y variable and if the sig value > 0.05 or tcount < ttable (1.681) then there is no effect of variable X on variable Y. The results of the t-test in this study are as follows:

Table 2. Partial Test Results (t)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	15.676	3.388		4.626	.000		
	Variabel_X1	.681	.123	.813	5.529	.000	.512	1.952
	Variabel_X2	-.080	.087	-.136	-.925	.360	.512	1.952

a. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

From the table above, the tcount value is 5,529. With = 5%, dk = 46-3 = 43, the ttable value is 1.681. From these numbers, it can be seen that tcount (5.529) > ttable (1.681), as well as the significance value of 0.00 < 0.05, it can be concluded that if the hypothesis is accepted, it means that there is an influence of the principal's leadership style on teacher performance in SMK Negeri 2 High cliff. Meanwhile, from the table above, the tcount value is -0.925. With = 5%, dk = 46-3 = 43, the ttable value is 1.681. From these numbers, it can be seen that tcount (-0.925) < ttable (1.681), as well as the significance value of 0.360 > 0.05, it can be concluded that if the hypothesis is rejected, it means that there is no effect of work motivation on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi. .

The f-test was used to determine whether the principal's leadership style and motivation variables simultaneously (simultaneously) had a significant effect on the teacher's performance variable. With the provisions, if the value of sig < 0.05 or fcount > ftable, then there is an effect between variable X simultaneously on variable Y, and if the value of sig > 0.05 or fcount < ftable then there is no simultaneous effect of variable X on variable Y. With the provisions of the table 2.82. The results of the fcount test in this study can be seen in the following table:

Table 3. Simultaneous Test Results (f)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	374.048	2	187.024	23.703	.000 ^b
	Residual	339.278	43	7.890		
	Total	713.326	45			

a. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), Variabel_X2, Variabel_X1

From the table above, the Fcount value is 23,703. With = 5%, df1=3, df2=46-3=43, the Ftable value is 2.82. From these numbers, it can be seen that Fcount (23.703) > Ftable (3.26), as well as the significance value of 0.000b < 0.05, it can be concluded, the hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is an influence of the principal's leadership style and work motivation on teacher performance. at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi.

The coefficient of determination (KD) is used to state the size of the contribution or contribution of variable X (leadership style and work motivation) to variable Y (teacher performance). The determination of the coefficient of determination is intended to determine the magnitude of the influence of the principal's leadership style and work motivation on teacher performance. The estimation accuracy test (R2) states the percentage of total variation of the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables in the model. The value of the coefficient of determination can be seen in the following table:

Table 4. Coefficient of Determination Results

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.724 ^a	.524	.502	2.809

a. Predictors: (Constant), Variabel_X2, Variabel_X1

b. Dependent Variable: Variabel_Y

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the value of Adjusted R Square is 0.502 or 50.2%. This shows that the principal's leadership style variable (X1) and work motivation (X2) can explain the teacher's performance variable (Y) by 50.2%, the remaining 49.8% (100% - 50.2%) is explained by the variable -Other variables not included in this study such as reward, punishment, communication, education level, years of service, work absentee level and so on were not careful in this study.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion that has been described, the following conclusions can be drawn:

The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

1. Multiple linear regression equation $Y = 15,676 + 0.681X_1 - 0.080X_2$. This means that the variables of the Principal's leadership style and work motivation have a significant relationship with the performance of teachers at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi.
2. The coefficient of determinant R^2 is 0.502 or 50.2%. This means that the principal's leadership style variable (X_1) and work motivation (X_2) can explain the teacher's performance variable (Y) by 50.2%, the remaining 49.8% (100% - 50.2%) is explained by other variables. which are not included in this study such as reward, punishment, communication, education level, years of service, work absentee level and so on that are not careful in this study.
3. The first hypothesis proposed states that there is an influence of the principal's leadership style on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi. After testing the hypothesis that the tcount value is 5.529. With = 5%, $dk = 46-3 = 43$, the ttable value is 1.681. From these numbers, it can be seen that tcount (5.529) > ttable (1.681), as well as the significance value of $0.00 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded if the hypothesis is accepted.
4. The second hypothesis proposed states that there is an influence of work motivation on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi. After testing the hypothesis that the value of tcount is -0.925. With = 5%, $dk = 46-3 = 43$, the ttable value is 1.681. From these numbers, it can be seen that tcount (-0.925) < ttable (1.681), as well as the significance value of $0.360 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded if the hypothesis is rejected.
5. The third hypothesis proposed states that there is an influence of the principal's leadership style and work motivation on teacher performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi. After being tested, the Fcount value is 23,703. With = 5%, $df_1=3$, $df_2=46-3=43$, the Ftable value is 2.82. From these numbers, it can be seen that Fcount (23.703) > Ftable (3.26), as well as the significance value of $0.000b < 0.05$, it can be concluded that the hypothesis is accepted.

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The Influence of Principal's Leadership Style and Work Motivation on Teacher Performance at SMK Negeri 2 Tebing Tinggi

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